

COMMON DISEASES OF WHEAT AND THEIR CONTROL METHODS

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Abstract

Agricultural workers know very well how difficult it is to protect grain crops from various diseases. Rust alone damages 5% of wheat per year, and more than 1% from bunt damage. In order to increase productivity, it is necessary to significantly reduce these diseases and pests. This article discusses how to recognize the symptoms of wheat lesions and what can be done to protect wheat.

Keywords. Wheat, wheat ear, wheat diseases, disease control, pests.

Аннотация

Сельскохозяйственные работники прекрасно знают, как трудно защитить зерновые культуры от различных болезней. Одна только ржавчина повреждает 5% пшеницы в год и более 1% от повреждения головней. Для повышения урожайности необходимо значительно снизить эти болезни и вредителей. В этой статье обсуждается, как распознать симптомы поражения пшеницы и что можно сделать для защиты пшеницы.

Ключевые слова. Пшеница, колос пшеницы, болезни пшеницы, борьба с болезнями, вредители.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is the most common cereal crop in the world. Therefore, huge areas are allocated for its cultivation. Flour, pasta and animal feed are made from this grain. But in order to save the harvest, it is necessary to monitor the condition of crops, take timely measures to fight against diseases and pests.

With an increase in humidity, pathogenic microflora appears in the wheat plant, which leads to the development of fungal diseases in it. Below we will consider the most common types of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Wheat can be affected by one of the varieties of rust, which is provoked by various fungi of the Basidiomycetes department:

1. Leafy (brown). Its causative agent is the fungus *Puccinia recondita*. Primary infection is often carried by airborne spores and develops slowly without serious consequences. In favorable conditions - high humidity and temperature around 20 ° C - the infection develops very quickly. It has the following features:

- appears in the form of round or oval pustules on the surface of the leaf plate (less often they can be seen in the internodes of the stem);
- pustules do not coalesce and contain orange or orange-brown uredospores produced every 10-14 days;
- during the stage of waxy ripening of the grains, in unfavorable weather conditions, many black teliospores are formed on the top.

2. Stem (black, striped). Derived from the fungus *Puccinia graminis*. Their intermediate bosses are barbers and mahogany. The conditions for the spread of infection are the same as for leaf rust. This disease manifests as dark brown pustules containing a mass of uredospores. They are formed not only on the stem, but also on the spikelets and on both sides of the leaves. With a strong infection, pustules merge with each other and tear the epidermis of the plant. Small tears and roughness on the surface of the affected tissue indicate infection.

RESULTS

Fungi belong to the *Tilletiaceae* and *Ustilaginaceae* families of the *Ustilaginales* or *fungi* family. They are characterized by the formation of mucous swellings or sacs in the reproductive or vegetative organs of the host plant, consisting of teliospores, the resting stage of the fungus. In species of the family *Tilletiaceae*, the teliospores develop into single-celled basidia with basidiospores (sporidia) on top. Representatives of the *Ustilaginaceae* family are characterized by the formation of 4-celled basidia or promycelium with lateral and apical basidiospores.

5 types of fungi parasitize wheat: *Tilletia caries*, *T. levis*, *Ustilago tritici*, *Tilletia indica*, *Uromyces tritici*, the first two types are the most common. Dwarf smut, despite its limited range, is very harmful. The infection of the smut diseases mainly occurs on the surface or inside the seeds, in some species on straw residues and in the soil. According to the nature of infection and the characteristics of plant infection, they are divided into 3 groups.

CONCLUSION

So, now you know what diseases and pests affect wheat (winter and spring). To protect the crop, try to take care of planting in time, remove weeds and loosen the soil. In addition, do not forget to observe the planting dates to reduce the possibility of contamination of the seed material. Fast-acting insecticides should be used for treatment.

References:

1. Абеленцев В.И. Факторы, снижающие эффективность протравливания семян хлебных злаков // Защита и карантин растений. 2007. №3. – С.28-29.
2. Абеленцев В.И. Фитосанитарные аспекты ресурсосберегающей технологии возделывания озимой пшеницы // Защита и карантин растений. 2009. №4. – С.46-49.
3. Аблова И.Б., Беспалова Л.А., Левченко Ю.Г. Желтая ржавчина пшеницы в Краснодарском крае и разнообразие генетических ресурсов по устойчивости к фитопатогену. Агротехнический метод защиты растений от вредных организмов. – Краснодар, 2011. –С.54-57.
4. Аблова И.Б., Беспалова Л.А., Колесников Ф.А., Набоков Г.Д. Устойчивость озимой пшеницы к твердой головне (*Tilletia caries* (DC) Tul). – Эволюция научных технологий в растениеводстве. – Краснодар, 2004. – С.336-342.
5. Абиев С.А., Есенгулова Б.Ж. Роль промежуточных хозяев ржавчинных грибов злаков // Вестник с.х. науки Казахстана. 1985. №8. –С.36-46.

